

The Disparity between Rural and Urban Areas in Level of Basic Education Services in the Municipality of Kenitra

SAFIR REDA

School of Teacher's College, Huzhou University, China

Abstract: This paper examines the significant disparities in public Primary education services between rural and urban areas within the municipality of Kenitra, Morocco. Despite efforts to improve education accessibility and quality, substantial gaps persist, adversely affecting the educational outcomes and opportunities for rural students. Through a comprehensive analysis of available data, including enrollment rates, infrastructure development, teacher allocation, and academic performance, this study elucidates the multifaceted dimensions of the rural-urban educational divide.

The findings underscore the acute shortage of educational infrastructure and resources in rural areas compared to their urban counterparts. Inadequate school facilities, limited access to educational materials, and a scarcity of qualified teachers exacerbate the educational inequities faced by rural students. Moreover, socio-economic disparities compound the challenges, as rural households often struggle with poverty and lack of access to essential services, further hindering children's educational attainment.

Addressing the rural-urban educational gap requires a holistic approach that integrates policy interventions, infrastructure development, and community engagement. Strategies such as targeted investment in rural schools, incentivizing teachers to work in remote areas, and implementing innovative teaching methodologies tailored to local contexts can help mitigate disparities and promote equitable access to quality education.

Furthermore, fostering partnerships between government agencies, non-profit organizations, and local communities is essential for mobilizing resources and expertise towards sustainable solutions. By prioritizing the needs of rural students and communities, policymakers can cultivate a more inclusive and equitable educational system that empowers all children to realize their full potential, regardless of their geographical location.

Keywords: Rural-urban disparity, Public Primary education, Kenitra municipality, educational infrastructure, Teacher allocation, Socio-economic factors, Equity in education.

*SAFIR REDA

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Introduction

Although schools - in general - serve a large segment of the population, represented by the student category, they have received less geographical attention, compared to other institutions. Such as: clinics and hospitals, which are frequented by fewer people than those who benefit from school services (Coleman and Collins, 2008).

Primary education schools represent the base of the educational pyramid, as they are the most numerous and spread widely spatially. Therefore, Primary education services are considered among the measures of spatial disparity in levels of human development, not only between countries or between regions of a single country, but also within a single region, through Studying the disparity between urban and rural areas in the level of Primary education school services. Education serves as the cornerstone of societal development, offering individuals the tools necessary to thrive and contribute to their communities. However, despite global efforts to ensure universal access to education, stark disparities persist, particularly between rural and urban areas. This phenomenon is strikingly evident in the municipality of Kenitra, Morocco, where significant gaps in public Primary education services continue to exist between rural and urban locales.

Kenitra, renowned for its economic dynamism and urban sprawl, stands as Morocco's largest city and a hub of industrial and commercial activity. Yet, within its boundaries lie rural areas characterized by agrarian economies, sparse populations, and limited access to essential services, including education. This spatial divide underscores a broader socio-economic cleavage that profoundly impacts the educational opportunities and outcomes of children residing in rural communities.

While urban centers benefit from relatively well-developed educational infrastructure, including schools equipped with modern amenities, qualified teachers, and supplementary resources, rural areas in Kenitra municipality grapple with systemic challenges. These challenges range from inadequate school facilities and insufficient teaching staff to socio-economic barriers that impede children's access to education. As a result, rural students often confront educational environments marked by resource scarcity, overcrowded classrooms, and substandard learning conditions, hindering their academic progress and prospects.

Understanding the roots and ramifications of the rural-urban educational disparity in Kenitra is imperative for crafting targeted interventions aimed at fostering educational equity and social inclusion. By delineating the factors contributing to this divergence, policymakers, educators, and stakeholders can devise evidence-based strategies to address the systemic inequities plaguing the public Primary education sector.

This paper seeks to explore the multifaceted nature of the rural-urban educational gap within the municipality of Kenitra, shedding light on its implications for educational access, quality, and outcomes. Through a comprehensive analysis of existing literature, statistical data, and qualitative insights, this study aims to inform discussions surrounding educational policy formulation, resource allocation, and community engagement initiatives geared towards bridging the rural-urban divide and advancing educational equity for all residents of Kenitra municipality.

The problem of the study and its questions:

Despite the many geographical studies that have dealt with the description and analysis of educational services, few of them have focused on showing the urban-rural disparity in the level of educational services. What is more, there is a geographical study in Morocco - to the researcher's knowledge - that deals with this topic, despite its scientific and practical importance. Therefore, this study focuses on analyzing the disparity between rural and urban areas in the level of Primary education services in the municipality of Kenitra. To understand this phenomenon and its geographical explanation.

This study aims to answer the following questions:

1. Is there a disparity between rural and urban areas in the municipality of Kenitra in the level of Primary education services?

2. What is the level of Primary education services in rural and urban areas of the municipality of Kenitra? Are these services below the planning standards prepared for this purpose? Or is it efficient when compared to these standards for Primary education services?

3. Do urban areas enjoy a better level of Primary education services than rural areas in the municipality of Kenitra? And why?

Aim of the study:

This study seeks to achieve the following:

1. Tracking the development of Primary education schools by rural and urban levels in the municipality of Kenitra.
2. Highlighting the disparities between rural and urban areas in the level of Primary education services in the municipality of Kenitra, through the use of some recognized indicators in studying educational services from a geographical perspective.
3. Comparing the indicators that highlight the variation in the level of Primary education services in rural and urban areas of the municipality of Kenitra, with some planning standards; This is to identify the efficiency of Primary education services, whether rural or urban, in the municipality of Kenitra.

The importance of the study:

1. This study is the first geographical study that seeks to highlight the difference between rural and urban areas in the level of Primary education services in Morocco, according to the researcher’s knowledge, so it could be the beginning of other geographical studies.
2. The researcher aspires for this study to be of interest and benefit to those in charge of managing the educational services sector in the municipality of Kenitra, through the results and recommendations that the study presents.
3. This study relies on several indicators to highlight the disparity between rural and urban areas in the level of Primary education services. Some of these indicators are used as standards for human development in Morocco, according to the Human Development Report in 2019, and the Human Development Report on Education in Morocco in 2022.

Fig. 1: Chart of population level and growth rate for the Kenitra, Morocco metro area from 2018 to 2023.

Research Methodology

This study relied on official statistics issued by the Educational Inspection Office in the Region of Grand Kenitra, for the academic year 2021-2022, as well as on the educational statistics for the municipality of Kenitra, prepared by the Ministry of Education of the Interim Government for the year 2022, and on unpublished data collected by the researcher from the Department of Technology and Maintenance of Educational Facilities in the municipality of Kenitra, on the areas of Primary education schools and the history of Build it in the municipality. The study data were analyzed through a quantitative analysis method, using analysis of variance One way Analysis of Variance And its abbreviation (ANOVA), The statistical program is known by (S.P.S.S).

Region Period	Rural		Urban		Total	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Before 1973	9	50	3	16	12	32
1973 - 1985	6	33	8	42	14	38
1986 - 1999	2	11	1	5	3	3
2000 - 2019	1	6	7	37	8	22
TOTAL	18	100	19	100	37	100

Table (2) Development of Primary education schools by rural and urban areas in the municipality of Kenitra

Based on the data in Table (2), the stages of development of Primary education schools in the municipality of Kenitra can be divided into four stages as follows:

1 The first stage (before 1791):

The number of Primary education schools in the municipality of Kenitra during this period reached (12) schools, representing 32% of the total number of Primary education schools currently in existence, which number (37) schools. The number of schools located in the countryside reached (9) schools, constituting half of the schools. The number of rural schools currently existing is (18). Schools located in the countryside constitute three-quarters of the Primary education schools in the municipality, while schools located in current urban areas represent only a quarter of the Primary education schools in the municipality of Kenitra. Likewise, Primary education schools do not represent Only 16% of the total Primary education schools in the municipality are located in urban areas. This is due to the increase in the number of Primary education schools in the countryside, there are about (6) schools in the current urban areas that were originally Primary education schools. They changed to be institutions of intermediate or higher education after the number of urban Primary education schools increased during subsequent periods.

2 The second phase (1973 - 1985):

After the year 1973, and the implementation of economic and social transformation plans in Morocco, the number of Primary education schools in the municipality of Kenitra that were established during this period reached (14) schools, constituting (38%) of the total Primary education schools in the municipality in 2019, six of which were located in the countryside; i.e. This represents a third of the existing Primary education schools in the countryside in 2019, while (8) Primary education schools were built in urban areas, and they represent (42%) of the Primary education schools currently located in urban areas. Therefore, the percentage of urban Primary education schools that were built during this period were (57%), compared to (43%) built in the countryside of Kenitra.

3 The third phase (1986 - 1999):

Due to the decline in oil prices since the mid-1980s, and the almost complete cessation of economic and social transformation plans in Morocco, only (3) Primary education schools were built in the municipality of Kenitra during this period, as they constituted only 8% of the total Primary education schools in The municipality in 2019, two of which are in the countryside, representing 11% of the total Primary education schools located in the countryside currently, while only one school was built in the urban area, representing 5% of the total Primary education schools located in urban areas in 2019.

4 The fourth stage (2000 - 2019):

Since the end of the 1990s, it has become clear that there is a shortage in the number of classes in Primary education schools in the municipality of Kenitra, especially in urban areas. Therefore, (8) Primary education schools were opened during this period, representing (22%) of the total Primary education schools in the municipality in 2019, seven of which were built in urban areas. Urban, which represents (8%) of the Primary schools in the city, while one Primary education school was built in the countryside and represents (6%) of the existing Primary education schools in the countryside of the municipality of Kenitra. Thus, the urban share of Primary schools built during this period amounted to (8.75%), while (5.12%) was the rural share.

Rural–Urban Educational Inequalities and Their Spatial Variations

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study sought to analyze the disparity between rural and urban areas in the level of Primary education services in the municipality of Kenitra, through eight educational indicators, and through the use of the single coefficient of variation, the study concluded the following results:

1. The study showed that there is a disparity between the rural and urban areas of the municipality of Kenitra in the average number of students in a school, as the student density in urban Primary education schools is approximately three times higher than the student density in Primary education schools in the countryside.
2. It became clear from the study that there is a fundamental disparity between rural and urban areas in the municipality of Kenitra in the average number of school classes. While the average number of classes in urban areas is (15) school classes, the average is (9) school classes in rural areas and clusters. The general average is (12) classrooms in the school at the level of Kenitra municipality in 2019.
3. The study concluded that there was a clear disparity between the rural areas of the municipality of Kenitra and its urban areas in class density. The average class density was (29) male and female students in Primary education schools located in urban areas, while the average was (18) male and female students in Primary education schools located in the countryside. At the municipal level, the average class density reached (24) male and female students in 2019.

4. The study revealed that the average number of teachers in Primary education schools in the municipality of Kenitra reached (43) male and female teachers, and this average increases in Primary education schools in urban areas to (51) male and female teachers, while the average in rural schools decreases to (35) male and female teachers in 2019.
5. As a result of the increase in the number of students in urban Primary education schools compared to schools located in the countryside, the (teacher/student) index in urban Primary Education schools reached one teacher for every (9) student, while the index in rural schools decreased to one teacher for every (5) student. The general index in Kenitra municipality was one teacher for every (8) student in 2019.
6. The study revealed that there was a disparity between the rural areas of the municipality of Kenitra and its urban areas in the average student share of the total school area, as the general average reached (27) square meters per student in the entire municipality in 2019, and due to the decrease in the number of students in rural Primary education schools, the rate increased It reached (38) square meters per student, while it decreased to (16) square meters in Primary schools located in urban areas. This rate is less than the planning standard, which ranges between (20-30) square meters per student, according to urban planning standards in Morocco.
7. The general average for the student's share of the built-up school area in the municipality of Kenitra was (6) square meters per student in 2019, while the average reached (5.8) square meters per student in Primary education schools in the countryside, while in Primary education schools located in urban areas, the rate decreased to about 4 square meters per student, which is below the level of urban planning standards for primary or middle schools in Morocco.
8. The study found a disparity between the rural areas of the municipality of Kenitra and its urban areas in school hours, as school hours are higher in Primary education schools located in urban areas, while they are less in rural Primary education schools. This is because many urban Primary schools use double shifts, as a result of classroom shortages.

Indicators of rural-urban disparity in the level of Primary education services:

As a result of the multiple indicators used in studying educational services in general, and Primary education services in particular, the study relied on eight indicators to measure the difference between rural and urban areas in the level of Primary education services in the municipality of Kenitra, according to the available data as follows:

First - Average number of students in the school:

Also - this indicator is called student density (Al-Saleh, 1986), and it is extracted by dividing the number of students by the number of schools. This indicator is one of the important indicators by which the efficiency and adequacy of Primary education services can be measured, whether rural or urban, and the table (3) It shows the disparity between rural and urban areas in the average number of students in school in the municipality of Kenitra in 2019

Table (4) The disparity between rural and urban areas in the average number of students in school in the municipality of Kenitra in 2019

Schools	Number	Average number of students in the school	Standard deviation
Rural area	18	173	98
Urban area	19	465	331
Overall average total	37	323	285
DF= 1 F Value=9.12 Sig= 0.001 < P			

It is clear from Table (4) that there is a disparity between rural and urban areas according to the index of the number of students in the school in the municipality of Kenitra. While the general average in the municipality is (323) male and

female students in each school, this average rises to (465) male and female students in each school. Primary education located in urban areas, while the indicator drops to (173) male and female students in each Primary education school located in rural areas and their clusters.

Statistical analysis revealed that this discrepancy between rural and urban areas in the average number of students in each school is a significant discrepancy, as it reached a significance level of $(0.001 < P)$; This is due to the fact that approximately three-quarters of students study in Primary education schools located in urban areas, compared to only a quarter of Primary education students whose schools are located in clusters and rural areas in the municipality of Kenitra. Table (5).

Table (5) Distribution of students in Primary education schools by rural and urban areas in the municipality of Kenitra in 2019.

Schools	Number of students	%
Rural area	3120	26
Urban area	8852	74
Total	11972	100

Second - Number of classes in the school:

This indicator is among the indicators used by researchers in studying educational services. It is extracted by dividing the number of classes by the number of schools (Zaitlin, 1996), and Table (6) shows the difference between rural and urban areas of the municipality of Kenitra, in the average number of classes in a school year 2019.

Schools	Numbers	The average number of classes in the school	Standard deviation
Rural area	18	2.9	8.1
Urban area	19	8.14	4.7
Total and overall average	37	12	6
DF= 1 F Value= 6.9 Sig= 0.004 < P			

It is clear from Table (6) that the average number of school classrooms in the municipality of Kenitra in 2017 is (12) school classrooms. The average for Primary education schools located in urban areas rises to about (15) school classrooms, while the average decreases to (9). School classes in rural areas and clusters. This indicates that there is a disparity between rural and urban areas in the municipality of Kenitra in the average number of classes in the school. The statistical analysis revealed that there is a fundamental disparity between rural schools and urban schools in the average number of classes in the school, as it reached the level of significance $(0.004 < P)$, Which indicates a clear disparity between them, linked to the number of classes in both rural and urban areas of the municipality of Kenitra. While 27% of classes are concentrated in Primary education schools located in urban areas, 37% of classes in these schools are located in rural areas and clusters in Kenitra Municipality, as shown in Table (7).

Table (7) Distribution of Primary education school classes by rural and urban areas in the municipality of Kenitra in 2019

Schools	Number of classes	%
Rural area	166	37
Urban area	281	63
Total	447	100

Third – Classroom’s Density:

Class density expresses the relationship between the number of students and the number of classes and is extracted by dividing the number of students by the number of classes. Class density is considered one of the most important indicators for evaluating educational services and measuring the disparity between rural and urban areas. Table (8) shows the disparity between the rural and urban areas of the municipality of Kenitra in Class density in 2019.

Table (8) Difference between rural and urban areas in classroom’s density in the municipality of Kenitra in 2019

School	Number	Classroom’s density	Standard deviation
Rural area	18	4.18	7.7
Urban area	19	6.28	5.7
Total and overall average	37	6.23	1.9
DF= 1 F Value= 6.16 Sig= 0.000 < P			

It is noted from Table (8) that the class density in the municipality of Kenitra is (24) male and female students per class, which is less than the planning standard in Morocco, which sets the maximum class density at thirty male and female students per class (Committee for the Evaluation of the Study on Regional and Local Plans, 2017) The class density in Primary education schools in urban areas increases to about (29) male and female students per class, and thus it almost conforms to the maximum planning standard, while the class density in Primary education schools in rural areas decreases to (18) male and female students per class, this density is less than the minimum planning standard in Morocco, which is (25) male and female students per class in the Primary education stage (Committee for the Evaluation of Studies on Regional and Local Plans, 2017).

When examining the difference in Classroom’s density between rural and urban areas in the municipality of Kenitra, it becomes clear that there is a fundamental difference at the level of significance (0,000<P), this disparity is due to some factors, the most important of which is the presence of about (75%) of students in the Primary education stage in the municipality of Kenitra in schools located in urban areas.

Fourth - Number of teachers in the school:

The average number of teachers in the school is one of the important indicators in studying and analyzing the level of efficiency of educational services and is an element for comparing the effectiveness of rural schools and urban schools. Table (9) shows the average number of teachers who actually teach, by rural and urban areas in the municipality of Kenitra in the year 2019.

Table (9) The disparity between rural and urban areas in the average number of school teachers in the municipality of Kenitra in 2019

School	Number	Average number of teachers in the school	Standard deviation
Rural area	18	8.34	5.10
Urban area	19	5.51	9.21
Total and overall average	37	4.43	19
DF= 1 F Value= 4.8 Sig= 0.006 < P			

It is noted from Table (9) that the average number of teachers reached (43) male and female teachers in the municipality of Kenitra in 2019, and these average reaches (51) male and female teachers in Primary education schools located in urban areas, while the average decreases to about (35) male and female teachers in public education schools. Rural Primary education, noting that this disparity - between rural and urban areas in the municipality of Kenitra in the indicator of the average number of teachers in the school - is described as significant, with a significance level of 0.006 (<P), which reflects that the level of Primary education services in urban areas is better than its counterpart in rural areas.

According to this indicator, the main factor behind this discrepancy lies in the difference in the number of teachers between the municipality’s countryside and urban areas, as Table (10) indicates that about (61%) of teachers in the Primary education stage work in schools located in urban areas, while (39%) Some of them work in rural schools in 2019.

Table (10) Distribution of teachers in the municipality of Kenitra by rural and urban areas in 2019

School	Number of teachers	%
Rural area	628	2.39
Urban area	728	8.60
Total	1606	100

Fifth - Indicator (teacher / student):

This indicator links the number of teachers to the number of students, and it represents the result of dividing the number of students by the number of teachers. This indicator is one of the important measures used to measure the disparity in levels of human development in the educational field, as it was used in the human development reports in Morocco for the years 2015 and 2019. Table (11) determines the degree of disparity between rural and urban areas in the municipality of Kenitra in the average number of students served by a teacher in 2019.

Table (11) The disparity between rural and urban areas in the municipality of Kenitra in the indicator (teacher / student) in the year 2019.

School	Number	Indicator (teacher/student)	Standard deviation
Rural area	18	7.4	5.1
Urban area	19	1.9	3.6
Total and overall average	37	9.6	1.5

DF= 1	F Value= 2.8	Sig= 0.007 < P
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It is clear from Table (11) that each teacher serves about (7) students as a general average in the municipality of Kenitra, and as a result of the student density in Primary education schools located in urban areas, the index rises to about (9) students per teacher, and on the contrary, the index decreases to about (5) One student per teacher in Primary education schools located in the countryside, due to their low student density, and the disparity between the rural and urban areas of the municipality of Kenitra - according to this indicator - is essentially statistically significant. (0.007 < P), and it should be noted here that the rate (teacher/student) in the countryside of the municipality of Kenitra is very close to the rate at the national level, which amounts to one teacher for every (5) student, while in the urban areas of the municipality of Kenitra, the rate is nearly double the rate. At the national level (UNICEF, National School Evaluation Program, 2019)

Sixth - Student rate from the total area of the school:

This rate expresses the relationship between the total area of schools and the number of their students. It represents the result of dividing the total educational space by the number of students. While this rate is a reliable basis for determining needs, it is also used in evaluating these services and studying future variations in educational services. Rural and urban areas in the level of educational services, and table (12) displays the disparity between rural and urban areas in the student rate per total area of the school in the municipality of Kenitra in 2019.

Table (12) The disparity between rural and urban areas in the student rate per total area of the school in the municipality of Kenitra in 2019.

School	Number	Student average per square meter (m ²) of the school's total area	Standard deviation
Rural area	18	1.8	2.2
Urban area	19	6.15	13
Total and overall average	37	6.26	7.21

DF= 1	F Value= 4.13	Sig= 0.001 < P
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From Table (12), the general average of the student's share of the total school area was about (27) square meters per student in the municipality of Kenitra, which is a rate that falls within the standard limits, as the planning standard ranges between (20-30) square meters per student. This The rate increases significantly in schools located in the countryside, reaching (38) square meters per student, and thus it exceeds the maximum planning standard by about eight square meters. However, in schools located in urban areas, the rate decreases to about (16) square meters per student, which indicates However it is below the planning standard.

The coefficient of variation revealed that there is a clear and significant difference between the rural areas of the municipality of Kenitra and its urban areas in the rate of students per total area of the school, as the significance level reached

(0.001 < P), and this reflects that the level of Primary education services in the countryside of the municipality of Kenitra, according to this indicator, is better. of Primary education services in urban areas. This disparity is linked to the lower density of students in rural schools compared to the density of students in urban schools.

This is reinforced by the fact that the school area in the countryside is close to the total area in urban areas, about (49%) of the total school area is located in the countryside, while (51%) of it is located in urban areas in 2019. In contrast, there

are only (26%) of Primary education students in rural areas and population centers, while (74%) of them study in Primary education schools located in urban areas (Table 13).

Table (13) Percentage distribution of the total school area and percentage of students by rural and urban areas of Kenitra Municipality in 2019.

School	Percentage of Primary education students	% of total school area
Rural area	26	7.48
Urban area	74	3.51
Total	100	100

Seventh - Student rate per built school area:

This rate is extracted by dividing the school area based on the number of students, and it is considered one of the important indicators when studying educational services. Because it reflects the degree of crowding of students within schools, and table (14) shows the disparity between rural and urban areas in the level of Primary education services in the municipality of Kenitra, through the student rate per built area of schools in 2019.

Table (14) The disparity between rural and urban areas in the student rate per built school area in the municipality of Kenitra in 2019.

School	Number	Student average of school-built area m2	Standard deviation
Rural area	18	5.8	2.5
Urban area	19	7.3	6.2
Total and overall average	37	6	7.4
DF= 1 F Value= 2.12 Sig= 0.001 < P			

Apparently, Table (14) that the general average of the student’s share of the built-up school area was (6) square meters per student in the municipality of Kenitra in 2019, which is a rate equal to the minimum planning standard for primary schools, which ranges between (6-8) square meters. For each student, which is less than the standard for middle schools, which ranges between (8-10) square meters per student (Committee for Evaluation of Studies on Regional and Local Plans 2019).

If we look at the average student share of the built-up school area in urban areas, it does not exceed (4) meters per student in 2019, which is therefore less than the planning standards referred to above, and it is also less than its counterpart in the countryside, which is about (8) square meters. per student, which falls within the limits of planning standards.

The disparity between rural and urban areas in the municipality of Kenitra in the average student share of the built-up school area is clear and significant, as the significance level of the disparity between them reached (0.001 <P); This urban-rural disparity is due to the high student density of urban schools, in contrast to schools located in rural areas and clusters.

Eighth - School hours:

This indicator refers to the periods of school use. As is known, schools are used during the morning period at a rate of five hours, and sometimes some schools use two periods, the first is called the morning period, and the second is called

the evening period. The number of school hours in these schools reached eight hours during the two periods, and Table (15) shows the disparity between the rural areas of the municipality of Kenitra and its urban areas in school hours in Primary education schools in 2019.

Table (15) Disparity between rural and urban areas of Kenitra municipality in working hours in Primary education schools in 2019

School	Number	School hours/hour	Standard deviation
Rural area	18	5	1
Urban area	19	7	1.4
Total and overall average	37	6	1.5
DF= 1 F Value= 3.25 Sig= 0.000 < P			

It is noted from Table (15) that the general average of school working hours in the municipality of Kenitra in 2019 is six hours per day, while the average for schools located in the municipality’s countryside is five hours. This means that Primary education schools in the municipality’s countryside operate for the morning period only, while secondary education school's Primary schools located in urban areas have working hours of up to seven hours a day, which indicates that a large percentage of them work in the morning and evening shifts, due to the high number of students compared to the number of classes.

The statistical analysis of the disparity between rural and urban areas in the municipality of Kenitra in school hours indicates the existence of a fundamental discrepancy with statistical significance amounting to (0,000 <P), which is linked to the presence of a shortage in the number of classes in schools located in urban areas, in light of the high student density therein. Compared to Primary education schools located in the countryside of Kenitra municipality.

The recommendations of this study are as follows:

1. The study revealed signs of student overcrowding in Primary education schools located in urban areas, especially in the cities of Kenitra, Mehdyia and Souk El Arbaa which requires increasing the number of classes in many existing schools.
2. The study revealed a low rate of student share of school space in schools located in urban areas, which requires the responsible authorities to address this deficiency, by making the number of students in these schools appropriate to their spaces, in accordance with the planning standards for Primary education schools.
3. Newly built schools, particularly after 2012 especially in urban areas, should undergo a detailed planning evaluation process; Because it was established by decisions of the Parliament, without adhering to urban planning standards for Primary education services.
4. Most Primary education schools in the municipality of Kenitra suffer from an overcrowding of teachers, so this problem should be addressed through a multi-stage plan, and in accordance with a specific educational policy.
5. Working to expand the number of classes according to needs in the cities of Kenitra, Mehdyia and Souk El Arbaa will play a major role in canceling the evening school period in many Primary education schools.

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REDA SAFIR, Huzhou University, China.